

The Conferences of John Cassian

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Entry tags: Christian monasticism, Asceticism, Latin Text, Religious Group, Text, Early Christian Monasticism in Egypt

This document was written in the 5th century by a monk named John Cassian in order to help found a monastery in the Roman-controlled region of Gaul (in modern-day France). The Conferences are the second volume of Cassian's instructions (the first volume is *The Institutes*) on how to correctly practice monasticism based on his experience living as a monk in Egypt. Unlike *The Institutes*, however, *The Conferences* is written as a series of conversations between a young Cassian, his monastic compatriot Germanus, and several venerable Egyptian monks. Conversations discuss the goals of monastic life, - principally "purity of heart" - and the correct practice of asceticism, - neither too lax nor too severe. There are also detailed discussions on theology, including the notion of God as unencumbered by a physical body, the possibility of humans uniting with God in spiritual perfection, and the influence of evil spirits on the mind and/or heart. This book gives a comprehensive vision of Cassian's ideal Egyptian monasticism in order to establish a similar institution in the West.

Date Range: 420 CE - 430 CE

Region: Southern Gaul

Region tags: Europe, Gaul

This was part of the Roman-controlled region of Gaul in what is now the southern coastal area of Marseille, France.

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Cassian, John, and Boniface Ramsey, translator. *John Cassian: The Conferences*. New York: Newman Press, 1997.
- Source 2: Casiday, Augustine. *Tradition and Theology in St John Cassian*. Oxford: Oxford Univ. Press, 2010.
- Source 3: Stewart, Columba. *Cassian the Monk*. New York: Oxford University Press, 1999.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://www.documentacatholicaomnia.eu/02m/0360-0435,_Cassianus_Ioannes,_De_Coenobiorum_Institutis_Libri_Duodecim,_MLT.pdf
- Source 1 Description: Online Latin version of the Conferences.

– Source 2 URL: <https://web-s-ebshost-com.du.idm.oclc.org/ehost/pdfviewer/pdfviewer?vid=0&sid=6afef8fb-776b-4709-8cc7-1d96e162aa44%40redis>

– Source 2 Description: Article entitled "Spiritual Encouragement in the Conferences of John Cassian"

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Written

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Papyrus

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: It's not funded by a polity as such. It is, however, commissioned and funded by a bishop of the region of Apta Julia in Gaul.

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Notes: While the word "Scripture" does not apply to this text, it is foundational for monasticism, and deeply informed the Rule of Benedict which in turn was the basis for all Western monastic rules.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The document is written in the colloquial Latin of its time. However, it is a deeply religious document, discussing as it does the inner life of the monk. Accordingly, many terms referring to sacred concepts such as "purity of heart" are the bedrock of the text.

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are no records of how many monks lived at the two monasteries for whom this text was intended. It was, presumably, a large monastery but how large is impossible to say.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Notes: Recruitment was not an important value, at least at the time of Cassian's writings. As he himself makes clear in the Institutes, postulants according to his rule had to pass a rigorous novitiate to even be allowed to become a monk.

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Notes: Not as such. However, Cassian found the already-established monasteries wanting in discipline and renunciation. According to him, reform was sorely needed.

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Notes: There are certainly references to ritual but it is not a ritual text as such.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Notes: The significance of this text lies only in the meaning of the words, not the medium.

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

Notes: The text is not Scriptural, as such. However, in the field of monastic studies, this text and its companion text the Institutes are significant enough to be considered a kind of canon.

Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– Yes

How are the volumes ordered?

–*Specify:* The Institutes is volume 1 while the Conferences is volume 2.

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Cultural with religious implications?

– No

Notes: This is written exclusively for monastics. While monasticism is certainly a kind of culture, the text does not apply to the larger culture of its time.

Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: The Conferences address the souls of monks, and this orientation includes the codification of behaviors around such topics as the proper practices of charity, prayer, and asceticism.

Other

–*Other [specify]:* While the Institutes addresses many practical concerns, such as daily scheduling, diet, and dress, The Conferences is oriented more toward the theology and inner experience of the monk.

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Notes: Since the Conferences is oriented toward inner experience and theology, it is not as prescriptive as the Institutes in terms of ritual. In addition, while it contains a few references to specialized vocabulary - mostly Greek words transliterated into Latin - they are not a significant focus of this text.

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

Notes: Cassian creates a lineage from Elijah and Elisha to John the Baptist to the Apostles to the earliest monks in Egypt. This lineage is not based on doctrine but rather on practices of asceticism and prayer.

Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: Rather than apostolic succession in which authority is passed down from Christ to the apostles to the bishops, Cassian creates a lineage from Elijah and Elisha to John the Baptist to the Apostles to the earliest monks in Egypt. This lineage is not based on doctrine but rather on practices of asceticism and prayer.

Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– No

How is the lineage established?

–Other [specify]: This lineage is not based on doctrine but rather on practices of asceticism and prayer which Cassian traces back to the original apostles, John the Baptist, and the prophets Elijah and Elisha.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: While the Institutes establishes daily routines of prayer and work, the Conferences emphasizes inner practices such as prayer and meditation on Scripture and what Cassian considers proper monastic theology.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– Yes

Notes: In the fourth conference, Cassian writes that spirit and flesh have an adversarial relationship. "The flesh delights in luxuries and pleasure, but the spirit does not give in even to natural desires." This is the basis for Cassian's emphasis on asceticism as the process of purification.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– No

Notes: The anthropology here is complicated, but Cassian writes in the fourth conference that "the desires of the flesh and the spirit exist in one human being." Both are necessary for the existence of the human being.

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– No

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– Yes

Notes: In the fourth conference, Cassian writes that the benefit to the conflict between flesh and spirit is that "the desire of the spirit [does not] let the mind be dragged into unrestrained wickedness, nor, on the other hand, does the frailty of the flesh permit the spirit to be inflated with unreasonable desires for virtue."

↳ Are there generally positive or negative associations with aggregates?

– Generally negative

Notes: Most states of mind are distrusted as being flesh-oriented and thus of a lower order than spiritual thoughts.

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

Notes: Mind-body dualism is generally taken for granted.

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

Notes: Late Antique conceptions of the soul were not incorporeal in the way modern people might conceive of them. Even the soul was material; it was just made of a material much more refined than the material of the body.

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– I don't know

Notes: Again, mind-body dualism was taken for granted in most of Greco-Roman philosophy and Late Antique Christianity.

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: "The heavens" are referred to but there is no "up" or "down" language as there is in other Christian literature. Rather, it refers to the afterlife as indicated by events, using language such as "the holy ones who are to reign in heaven with the Lord."

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Notes: Not specifically. It is always something that is to come at an unspecified time in the future.

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Notes: In fact, the afterlife plays a very small part in the this text which generally focuses on monastic spiritual development here and now.

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Notes: Funereal practices are not referred to in this text.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– No

Notes: In the fourth conference, the text refers to "demons and evil spirits" which are incorporeal and thus able to influence the thoughts and desires of monks. They are said to be fallen angels.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: We might say that a monk can "feel" the demons and evil spirits when they bring about unwholesome desires in the mind and body of the monk.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– No

Notes: There is no reference to this. Rather, the demons have knowledge of the minds of monks and can thus influence their thoughts.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– No

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– No

Notes: Not exactly, but demons can influence monks through thoughts and desires to behave in ways that may incur punishment.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life?

– Yes

Notes: But only through thoughts, not as physical entities speaking to monks.

↳ In dreams?

– Yes

↳ In trance possession?

– No

↳ Through divination practices?

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists?

– No

Notes: Monks are told to constantly examine their thoughts for impurity which is taken to be of demonic origin.

↳ Only through monarch?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

Notes: Demons don't or can't create physical action themselves, being incorporeal. They do, however, affect the thoughts and desires of monks and can therefore cause monks to act for them if the monks are not vigilant.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– No

Notes: Demons are not "characters" in this text and therefore exhibit no emotion. In other examples of monastic literature there are stories of embodied demons who become angry, afraid, or frustrated when their evil intentions are thwarted.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Notes: Being bodiless, demons in this text cannot feel hunger.

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Notes: Demons are not given names in this text. They are referred to generally as evil spirits influencing thoughts and desires of those trying to purify themselves through asceticism.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: Since this text states that demons are incorporeal, the only sense in which they are physically present is through any actions taken by a monk under demonic influence.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: At this stage in Late Antique monasticism, divination practices would likely have been deemed either evil or heretical, although it is not discussed in this text.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the 9th conference which deals with prayer, Cassian writes that prayer is always answered if it is in accord with the divine will. In this case, divine monitoring has more to do with inner intentions than outer behavior, although the Institutes makes clear that behavior matters to the deity as well.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– No

Notes: While this could be implied from the context, taboos are generally not a concern of the Conferences.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

Notes: Again, this is probably the case but not addressed explicitly.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

Notes: Yes, but since monks are required to be celibate, this is not emphasized in the text.

↳ Incest

– Yes

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– I don't know

Notes: This is not explicitly mentioned in the text.

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– No

Notes: This text encourages total obedience to one's superior in a monastery. Therefore, Cassian seems unconcerned with the possibilities of abuse by superiors, assuming apparently that all superiors act their subordinates' welfare in mind.

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

↳ Other sexual practices

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: The text assumes that God sees the hearts/minds of all people and will thus know immediately if anyone is lying. An important part of monastic training, according to Cassian is making oneself as mentally transparent to one's superior as one is to God.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: This can be assumed, but is not addressed in this text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– Yes

Notes: This is only evident in this text by Cassian's concern with laziness. Monks are supposed to be either working, praying, or both all the time.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: Again, this can be assumed but is not explicitly addressed in the text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders

– Yes

Notes: The superior of a monastery acts in the place of God. Thus these superiors must be respected and obeyed.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping

– Yes

Notes: In other concurrent monastic literature, gossip is talked about as an important sin to avoid. In Cassian, the phrase "idle chatter," which includes gossip, is seen as a distraction from the important work of prayer.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes

– Yes

Notes: This is true, but not because private property is a value of this text. Rather, if one is stealing, one has yet to truly renounce worldly things as one should to be a true monk.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance

– Yes

Notes: In the Institutes, the proper performance of worship is outlined with precision. In the Conferences, the notion that how and when one performs worship is significant is reinforced.

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals

– Yes

Notes: See previous answer.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists

– No

Notes: Those outside Christianity are hardly acknowledged in this text.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness

– Yes

Notes: This is mostly evidenced by references to the requirement that monks be charitable toward those in need.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene

– No

Notes: Bathing was considered a luxury and thus those who had not bathed for many years as part of their ascetic practice are lauded.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– No

Notes: While everyone in the monastery has responsibilities for its upkeep, this is an earthly duty, not a heavenly, one.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?

– No

↳ Done randomly

– No

↳ Other

– Yes

Notes: Divine punishments are understood to come at the end of life when one is either rewarded for behaving and believing in the true faith or punished for not doing so.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group

– Yes

Notes: This and other monastic texts emphasize the importance of remembering the possibility of divine punishment if one misbehaves or goes astray in terms of practice or theology.

↳ Punishments in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure

– No

Notes: No, suffering is severe.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure?

– Yes

Notes: The usual reference is to torturous fires.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form?

– No

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm?

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?

– No

Notes: While not impossible, the references made in this text are exclusively to the afterlife in regard to divine punishment.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?

– Yes

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?

– Yes

Notes: Monks are told to both contemplate the danger of divine punishment and the incentive of divine reward.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?

– No

↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?

– Yes

Notes: This is often not specified, but the implication is a place of divine bliss and safety.

↳ Consists of eternal happiness?

– Yes

↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?

– No

↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?

– Yes

Notes: In general, the text explains rewards in this lifetime consists of divine grace. Grace is bestowed upon the monk as a result of the effort he makes in asceticism and righteous behavior (see Conference 13). This grace then reinforces the efforts of the monk. Cassian makes it clear that mere human effort will never be sufficient without divine grace. One could also see the respect and fame diligent monks receive as divine rewards, although Cassian warns that these are a threat to the main virtue monks are supposed to cultivate: humility.

- ↳ Highly emphasized?
 - No

- ↳ Consists of good luck?
 - No

- ↳ Consists of political success or power?
 - No
 - Notes: These are to be rejected by true monks, according to Cassian, since they diminish humility.

- ↳ Consists of success in battle?
 - No

- ↳ Consists of peace or social stability?
 - No

- ↳ Consists of healthy crops or good weather?
 - No

- ↳ Consists of success on journeys?
 - No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health?
 - No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success?
 - No

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants?
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: I answer yes here merely to acknowledge that Cassian and his form of monasticism are Christian and thus believe that Jesus was the messiah, that he came already and will come again at an unspecified time in the future. This is assumed in this text and so not emphasized.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– No

↳ Other purpose

–Specify: His salvific death saves people from death, granting them (conditional) eternal life.

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Notes: All Christian writings of this period assume an eschatology. This is not the emphasis of this text, however.

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: A general kindness and compassion in treatment of others are encouraged, especially in Conference 11. Monks are also told never to judge anyone but themselves, since they will likely take on the sins that they condemn.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Notes: This is not emphasized here.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: Honesty here applies especially to revealing all one's thoughts to one's superior.

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: See especially Conference 11 chapter 10.

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Notes: This is part of not judging which is highly emphasized in this text.

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Notes: This accords with the frequent stressing of the importance of humility.

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

Notes: Purity of heart, which Cassian talks about, is an inner state free from passion, not a ritual condition.

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

Notes: Monks are required to abandon all family ties so that nothing ties them to the secular world.

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

Notes: This applies mainly to the loyalty and obedience to one's superior required in this text.

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Notes: In a monastery, all must work together to maintain the community.

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

Notes: Monks are deprived of all personal goods, according to Cassian. They have use of the resources of the monastery but not ownership.

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

Notes: In conference 18, Cassian writes that "true patience and tranquillity is neither gained nor retained without profound humility of heart." Again, humility is seen as the foundation of all other virtues.

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Notes: Diligent effort at asceticism, prayer, and good behavior is essential, although Cassian acknowledges that these will be insufficient without God's grace.

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Notes: Again, for Cassian this is the foundation of all the other virtues.

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

Notes: This is the result of the attainment of the state free from passion which Cassian calls "purity of heart."

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

Notes: In Conference 9, Cassian writes of four types of prayer, the last of which is Thanksgiving: "Then in the fourth place there stand thanksgivings which the mind in ineffable transports offers up to God, either when it recalls God's past benefits or when it contemplates His present ones, or when it looks forward to those great ones in the future which God has prepared for them that love Him."

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: Wisdom is seen as the result of the attainment of purity of heart.

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Notes: In conference 2, Cassian writes of the importance of developing discernment in order to know when one's thoughts and/or desires are being influenced by demonic powers.

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Notes: Even nocturnal emissions are a sign that one has not yet achieved purity of heart (see Conference 22).

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Total abstinence is required.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is important as an instrumental good. In Conference 21, Cassian writes, "For our endeavor must be that those virtues which are really good may be gained by fasting." In other words, fasting is not an end or a good in itself.

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– Yes

Notes: The monastic diet should be simple. Gluttony is tied to sexual impurity and is one of the 8 principal vices in the Institutes.

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– Yes

Notes: When a monk enters the monastery, he is stripped of all his worldly goods, including his clothing (which is replaced by monastic robes).

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– Yes

Notes: This text focuses far less on communal prayer and the daily schedule of monks than the Institutes, but there are scattered references. In addition, in Conference 10, Cassian writes that the monk must try to pray continuously in his heart, no matter what else he is doing.

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: Again, these are outlined more precisely in the Institutes, but righteous behavior is significant in the Conferences.

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances?

– I don't know

Notes: Again, monks are asked to try to "pray without ceasing," that is, all the time, whether silently or aloud.

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– Yes

↳ On average, how many participants gather in one location?

– I don't know

Notes: It just depends on the size of the monastery.

↳ Interval of time between performances (in hours)

– I don't know

Notes: This applies to communal prayers.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Yes

Notes: Each monk visits with his superior and reveals his thoughts and actions frequently. Also, the daily schedule of work and prayer makes sure that monks are practicing correctly.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices?

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification?

– No

↳ Circumcision?

– No

↳ Food taboos?

– Yes

Notes: Certainly, monks are to keep their diets simple and not luxurious.

↳ Hair?

– Yes

Notes: Hair and beards are left long and unkempt.

↳ Dress?

– Yes

↳ Ornaments?

– No

↳ Archaic ritual language?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is universal?

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology is widespread?

– Yes

Notes: Monks call each other "brothers," while superiors are called "fathers."

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A Spiritual Elect

Notes: Monasteries are societies within societies. They are set apart from the larger world and have their own customs and culture.

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– Yes

Notes: Conference 14 speaks of many virtuous activities in which monks may participate, one of which is giving alms to the poor.

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– Yes

Notes: Hospitality for travelers is one of the functions of a monastery.

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: Cassian, who is well-educated himself, implies that those with the best educations often fall short in the virtues and purity of heart.

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Notes: While the text speaks of fasting and eating, it does not detail how food is produced or distributed.

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